

PREPARATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF GREEN COMPOSITE USING BIOMIMETIC MODIFIED LIGNIN

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ABSTRACT

In this study, two types of alkyl-chain modification agents, l-lactic acid and tetrahydrofuran are used. Cellulose is compatible with hemicellulose, which is coupled to lignin by ether, glycoside and ester bonds in plant. To mimic this structure, in this study, lignin is combined with an alkyl chain with a similar SP value that used as a matrix polymer, PLA. This relationship between lignin and the alkyl chain is similar to that between cellulose and lignin carbohydrate complex(LCC). The results of 1-H NMR analysis confirm the modification. DSC analyses demonstrated that differences in thermal properties between lignin and modified lignin arose. Furthermore, it is observed that the thermal and physicochemical properties of modified lignin/PLA blend could be adjusted according to the characteristics of the alkyl chains. All mechanical properties of PLAL/PLA is decreased by modification. Mechanical properties of 40:60 (PLAL/PLA) decreased remarkably while those of 20:80 decreased a little. THFL/PLA blends show the better mechanical properties that PLAL/PLA even though the good compatibility is expected in the case of PLAL/PLA. As a result, the physical properties of the resulting blends were limited by alkyl chain of modified lignin. It can be confirmed that type of alky chain and miscibility gap between alkyl chain-matrix affect mechanical properties enormously in the fungi degradable environment.

1.Introduction

Lignin has enormous potential as a raw material for polymer industries. But, lignin has not been utilized well as a raw material because of its brittleness and difficulty to be processed. Therefore, chemical modification of lignin is a big issue of the lignin research area. Main idea of chemical modification is to replace the carboxyl group and hydroxyl group of lignin by alkylation, acylation and hydroxyalkylation. The theoretical basis is based on the fact that lignin exists in the form of lignin carbohydrate complex(LCC) in plants. Proto lignin forms a covalent bond with hemicellulose chemically via a ester bond or ether bond in plants. And the reagents are chemically bonded with lignin to mimic that LCC structure. (Fig. 1.)

The structure of LCC was a subject of controversy for a long time. Today, however, it is well established that LCC is composed of hemicellulose chemically bound to lignin. This structure agrees with that proposed by the theory of lignin biosynthesis and has also been demonstrated by electron microscopy. LCC have been proposed to be composed of a covalent bond with the hydroxyl group of an aromatic ring of lignin, combined with the ester bond or the ether linkage of hemicellulose side chain, and there is evidence of such structures. In this study, two types of reagent with different solubility parameter (SP) were chemically combined with lignin to mimic the LCC structure.

Figure 1. Scheme of lignin modification

2.Experimental

2.1 Materials and Methods

Oligomerized-(lactic acid) is prepared for Poly Lactic Acid modified lignin(PLAL). 1wt% Lactic acid is used as a chemical modification catalyst. In order to prepare Tetrahydrofuran modified lignin(THFL), lignin is modified with 1 wt% sulfuric acid as catalyst. Lignin is purchased from MeadWestVaco, Indullin AT, SKL. Chemically modified lignin is blended with Poly Lactic Acid(PLA) (Tg - 70°C, Mw - 80,000) as matrix. The blends of modified lignin and PLA are prepared with different weight ratio of 20:80, 40:60, 60:40. Figure 2(a). shows degradability test using fungi, *Aspergillus awamori* using saboraud agar. This test is accelerate land-fill degradation test. In order to investigate change of mechanical property and weight loss according to the time, 4, 8 and 12 week, 5 samples were placed in each petri dish. Figure 2(b) shows SEM image of neat PLA that 1 month land-fill tested. PLA is a typical bulk erosion material in a hydrolysis condition as shown in Figure 2.(b). The medium was prepared on the basis of the BD Difco's manual and was sterilized in autoclave. Subsequently, both sides of a petri dish (90 mm x 15 mm) were coated with 15 ml of medium, and the fungi were seeded. At 25°C and 80%RH(relative humidity), the fungi were grown for 96 hours. Afterwards, the the blend of 75% polymer and 25% modified lignin was placed on the middle of the medium-coated surfaces(number of samples = 5).Fungi were allowed to degrade the sample for 4 weeks, 8 weeks, and 12 weeks (Fig. 2), and the samples were washed in soapy water for 30 minutes and then washed in distilled water for 30 minutes. The washed sample was stored in a desiccator for 24 hours to remove the residual water. Finally, the decreases in sample weight and changes in mechanical properties were measured.

Figure 2. Degradation study of lignin composite (a) fungi degradation test (b) degradation of PLA

2.2 Characterization

1H-NMR

To investigate the chemical properties of the lignin and modified lignin, ¹H-NMR spectra of the samples were obtained using a 400 MHz NMR spectrometer (JeolJNM-LA400 with LFG, JEOL, JAPAN).

Thermal Properties

A differential scanning calorimeter (DSC-Q1000,TA Instrument Inc., UK) is used to investigate the thermal transition behavior of modified lignin and modified lignin/PLA blends.

Mechanical Properties

A universal testing machine (LRXPlus, LLOYD Instruments Inc., UK) is used to investigate the tensile properties of the modified lignin/PLA blends.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 1H-NMR

Figure 3. 1H-NMR analysis of lignin and modified lignin

As shown in Figure 3, the aromatic OH(ArOH) and aliphatic OH(AIOH) of lignin are reduced significantly in both PLAL and THFL. This indicates that as the result of the FT-IR, lignin is substituted with an alkyl chain by modification agents. Furthermore, the alkyl chain that replaces the hydroxyl group of the lignin reduced the brittle nature of the lignin. THFL shows low block yield (37.2 %) and has more remaining ArOH (9.86 ppm) and AIOH (3.88 ppm) compared with that of PLAL.[1] PLAL is modified by the alkyl chain and shows high yield of block OH(91 %).(Table 1.) Furthermore, modification is confirmed by the presence of the specific PLA signal near 5.0 ppm. Although almost the same amount reagent was used and the modification yields showed little difference (41.5 wt% vs. 31.7wt%), the yield of block OH and terminal hydroxyl group (free OH)of the alkyl chain showed large differences.

SAMPLE	ArOH (peak intensity)	AIOH (peak intensity)	Block Yield (% of peak intensity decrease)
Lignin	0.026	0.36	0%
PLAL	0.002	0.04	91%
THFL	0.02	0.175	37.2%

Table 1. Yield of the lignin OH block by 1-H NMR analysis

3.2 Thermal Properties

Figure 4. DSC analysis of modified lignin/PLA blend

The DSC analysis shows that phase change of modified lignin and PLA with different blend ratio. (Fig. 4.) However, when the ratio of PLA blends with different modified lignin, it can be found that the addition of modified lignin, the thermal properties of PLA is changed.[2] Figure 4.(b) shows a small melting peak near the T_m of PLA. It is regarded as a melting of THFL, and it is evidence of the phase separation between THFL/PLA caused by the low compatibility between THFL and PLA. Furthermore, it is observed that the thermal and physicochemical properties of modified lignin/PLA blend could be adjusted according to the characteristics of the alkyl chains.

3.3 Mechanical Properties

Figure 5. Mechanical properties of (a) PLAL-PLA blend and (b) THFL-PLA blend

All mechanical properties of PLAL-PLA is decreased by modification. Mechanical properties of 40:60 (PLAL/PLA) decreased remarkably while those of 20:80 decreased a little. THFL/PLA blends show the better mechanical properties that PLAL/PLA even though the good compatibility is expected in the case of PLAL/PLA.(Fig. 5.)

3.4 Degradability Test

	Neat	4week	8week	12week
Ultimate Tensile Strength (MPa)	40.9	12.45	13	19
Strain at break(%)	5.86	3.8	1.76	1.55
Young's Modulus (GPa)	1.6	1.53	2	2.7

Table 2. Tensile Properties and Weight loss of THFL/PLA-4/6 Blends according to the degradation time

Table 2 shows change of mechanical property according to the degradation time. It seems that strength and strain decrease gradually and modulus increase gradually. This is because chain degradation makes materials 'brittle', as shown in the bulk erosion process or photo-degradation of polymers that increasing crystallinity.[3,4] Amorphous region is hydrolyzed in a degradation process by the time progress. [5]

4. Conclusions

The results of NMR analysis indicate that the OH groups of lignin had been well replaced with alkyl chains through modification. DSC analyses demonstrated that the thermal and physicochemical properties of modified lignin/PLA blend could be adjusted according to the characteristics of the alkyl chains. THFL/PLA blends show the better mechanical properties than PLAL/PLA even though the good compatibility is expected in the case of PLAL/PLA. It is also backed up by the fact that PLAL has low T_g. As a result, the physical properties of the resulting blends were limited by alkyl chain of modified lignin. After active biodegradation occurred, the lamellar structure of the blend was weakened

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